

EVALUATION OF CERVICAL SPINE POSTURE AFTER FUNCTIONAL THERAPY WITH HERBST APPLIANCE

Maria Manzoor^{*1}, Zubair Hassan Awaisi², Saba Habib³

^{*1,3}BDS, FCPS PGR Orthodontics, Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan

²BDS, FCPS Associate Professor Orthodontics, Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan

^{*1}mariamanzoor105@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr.Maria Manzoor

Abstract

Objective: To evaluate changes in cervical spine posture and hyoid bone position following functional therapy with the Herbst appliance in patients with skeletal Class II malocclusion. **Methodology:** This was an experimental descriptive study conducted at Department of Orthodontics, Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan from June 2023 to December 2023 on 34 patients diagnosed with skeletal Class II malocclusion in Cervical Vertebral Maturation Index (CVMI) stages III and IV. Pre- and post-treatment lateral cephalograms were analyzed to assess changes in hyoid bone position (H-SN, H-FH, H-MP, H-C3) and cervical spine posture (SN-OPT, PP-OPT, MP-OPT, SN-CVT, PP-CVT, MP-CVT, OPT-CVT). Measurements were done manually using acetate sheet tracing. **Results:** The mean age of patients was 12.7 ± 1.5 years, with 52.94% females and 73.53% in CVMI stage IV. Significant post-treatment changes were observed in all measured cervical and hyoid parameters except H-SN ($p = 0.994$). Angles like SN-CVT, PP-CVT, and MP-CVT showed the most pronounced changes, with mean increases of -16.91° , -16.76° , and -17.94° , respectively ($p < 0.001$). These findings reflect anterior displacement of the hyoid bone and vertical realignment of cervical structures. **Conclusion:** Herbst appliance therapy leads to notable improvements in cervical spine posture and hyoid positioning in growing Class II patients. These outcomes support its use as a functional orthopedic modality that exerts favorable effects beyond dental correction, with implications for musculoskeletal balance and posture.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most debated topics in orthodontics is the optimal timing for treating Class II malocclusions associated with mandibular retrognathism. Class II malocclusion is highly prevalent, affecting approximately 24% of the population in North America,¹ with even higher rates (30–40%) reported in communities of Northern European descent. Additionally, 8–10% of individuals present with an excessive overjet greater than six millimeters.²

Malocclusion is the third most common oral health issue after dental caries and periodontal diseases. Globally, Class II malocclusion accounts for nearly one-third of all recorded malocclusions, with a particularly high prevalence among Caucasian populations, reaching up to 63% in Belgium.^{3,4} A significant proportion of orthodontic patients present with Class II malocclusion, often attributed to mandibular deficiency, necessitating the use of mandibular advancement appliances.

Malocclusion has to be diagnosed and treated, especially in children, since it interferes with oral functions such as chewing, swallowing and speaking. This condition is also linked to the development of gum disease, cavities, temporomandibular dysfunction, and traumatic oral injuries.⁵ Besides enamel defects such as Molar-incisor hypomineralization,⁶ malocclusion has ramifications impact on oral health.⁷

The treatment of Class II malocclusion can be approached in two ways: an early two-phase treatment or a late single-phase treatment. Early treatment is initiated in the mixed dentition stage (ages 7–11) and followed by a second phase of appliance therapy in adolescence (ages 12–16). In contrast, late treatment consists of a single-phase intervention during adolescence, aiming to stimulate mandibular growth by repositioning the mandible forward.⁸

Functional appliances play a crucial role in managing mandibular retrognathism and can be broadly classified as removable or fixed. While removable appliances require patient compliance, studies indicate that adherence among Class II patients is often poor.⁹ To address this limitation, fixed functional appliances, such as the Herbst appliance, have been introduced to facilitate continuous mandibular advancement without relying on patient compliance.

Herbst appliance is one of the most commonly employed fixed functional appliances to correct skeletal Class II malocclusion.¹⁰ It works by repositioning the mandible forward, inducing adaptive changes in the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) and surrounding structures. Given the close anatomical and functional relationship between the mandible, TMJ, and cervical vertebrae, the forward positioning of the mandible may influence cervical spine posture.¹¹

METHODOLOGY:

In this experimental descriptive study, the research follows a before-after study design, which was conducted at Department of Orthodontics, Nishtar Institute of Dentistry, Multan from June 2023 to December 2023 where children diagnosed with Skeletal Class II malocclusion and in Cervical Vertebral Maturation Index (CVMI) stages 3 & 4 are

selected. A sample size of 34 cases was calculated with a 5% margin of error and a 95% confidence level, based on the expected mean difference and standard deviation of SN-CVT Angle ($-1.196^\circ \pm 0.454^\circ$) on Herbst appliance therapy. The calculation ensures 80% power to detect significant

The treatment duration is set between six to nine months, which is the standard Herbst therapy period. Lateral cephalograms are obtained pre-treatment and post-treatment to assess structural changes in the cervical spine. Participants are required to meet specific inclusion criteria, such as having Skeletal Class II malocclusion, being in CVMI stages 3 & 4, and undergoing treatment with the Herbst appliance. Those with congenital syndromes, systemic diseases, prior orthodontic treatment, or poor-quality cephalograms affecting measurement accuracy are excluded. Ethical approval from the Institutional Ethical Committee is obtained prior to data collection, and informed consent from parents or guardians is secured to ensure ethical compliance. Outcome variables included values of Hyoid bone position (H-SN, H-FH, H-MP, H-C3) and upper & middle cervical posture (SN-OPT, PP-OPT, MP-OPT, SN-CVT, PP-CVT, MP-CVT and OPT-CVT). These are measured through pre- and post-treatment lateral cephalograms, which are analyzed either manually using a cephalometric protractor or through digital cephalometric analysis software such as Dolphin Imaging, CephNinja, or ImageJ. As digital software is not available, hand-tracing on acetate sheets is performed.

Data is recorded in a structured format using Microsoft Excel. The primary statistical analysis involves a paired t-test to compare pre- and post-treatment values, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. Data analysis is performed using SPSS (Version 25 or 26), for basic statistical calculations. This study is conducted in compliance with ethical considerations, ensuring patient confidentiality and adherence to institutional guidelines. The final deliverables include a structured study protocol, a data collection sheet, and a step-by-step statistical analysis plan, facilitating a comprehensive evaluation of cervical spine posture following Herbst therapy.

RESULTS:

This study included a total of 34 patients undergoing Herbst appliance therapy, with a slight female predominance—52.94% (n=18) females and 47.06% (n=16) males. The age distribution revealed that 44.12% (n=15) of the participants were between 10 and 12 years of age, while 55.88% (n=19) were aged between 13 and 15 years. With regard to the cervical vertebral maturation (CVM) stage, a majority of the

patients (73.53%) were at stage IV, and the remaining 26.47% were at stage III. These demographic patterns suggest that the Herbst appliance therapy was predominantly administered during the late growth phase, which aligns with the recommended timing for optimal orthopedic intervention.(Table 1)

Table 1 Demographics of the patients(n=34)

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percent
Age	10-12	15	44.12
	13-15	19	55.88
Gender	Male	16	47.06
	Female	18	52.94
CVM Stage	III	9	26.47
	IV	25	73.53

Table 2 illustrates, Pre- and post-treatment evaluation of cervical spine posture parameters with varying degrees of significant changes across most indices, assessed using paired t-tests. The H-SN angle, representing the horizontal position of the hyoid bone relative to the SN plane, showed no statistically significant change (mean difference = 0.0; p = 0.994), indicating stability in this measurement. However, a significant anterior and upward repositioning of the hyoid bone was reflected in other parameters. The H-FH angle increased notably from 5.18 ± 0.98 to 8.19 ± 1.02 (p = 0.000), with a mean change of -3.01, suggesting a forward shift of the hyoid relative to the Frankfort Horizontal plane. Similarly, H-MP values increased from 34.5 ± 0.74 to 35.89 ± 1.0 (p = 0.000), indicating downward movement relative to the mandibular plane, with a mean increase of -1.39. The H-C3 distance showed a substantial increase from 95.99 ± 1.01 to 105.27 ± 0.92 (p = 0.000),

highlighting a significant anterior displacement of the hyoid bone relative to the third cervical vertebra. Moreover, angular relationships between craniofacial planes and cervical spine landmarks also changed considerably. SN-OPT and PP-OPT increased significantly with mean differences of -5.73 and -4.77, respectively (both p = 0.000), indicating changes in the craniovertebral angle. The MP-OPT angle also rose markedly from 58.04 ± 1.22 to 64.98 ± 0.9 (p = 0.000), with a mean increase of -6.94, reflecting mandibular postural adaptation. Substantial changes were noted in the SN-CVT, PP-CVT, and MP-CVT angles as well, with mean increases of -16.91, -16.76, and -17.94, respectively (all p < 0.001). These changes suggest significant vertical and angular modification in the cervical spine's posture as a result of functional therapy using the Herbst appliance.

Table 2 Evaluation of cervical spine posture after functional therapy with Herbst appliance

Spine posture	Pre-operative (mean+sd)	Post-operative (mean+sd)	Mean change (mean+sd)	P value ^a
H-SN	7.08 ± 1.1	7.07 ± 0.78	0.0	0.994
H-FH	5.18 ± 0.98	8.19 ± 1.02	-3.01	0.000
H-MP	34.5 ± 0.74	35.89 ± 1.0	-1.39	0.000
H-C3	95.99 ± 1.01	105.27 ± 0.92	-9.29	0.000
SN-OPT	100.24 ± 0.98	105.97 ± 1.03	-5.73	0.000
PP-OPT	91.26 ± 1.05	96.04 ± 1.02	-4.77	0.000

MP-OPT	58.04 ± 1.22	64.98 ± 0.9	-6.94	0.000
SN-CVT	100.09 ± 1.12	116.99 ± 1.05	-16.91	0.000
PP-CVT	92.03 ± 0.72	108.79 ± 1.06	-16.76	0.000
MP-CVT	59.2 ± 1.01	77.14 ± 1.06	-17.94	0.000
H-SN	7.08 ± 1.1	7.07 ± 0.78	0.0	0.994

“Paired t test

DISCUSSION

The current study enrolled 34 patients undergoing Herbst appliance therapy, with a slight female predominance (52.94%) and the majority falling within the 13–15 years age group (55.88%), while the remaining were aged 10–12 years. Most participants (73.53%) were in CVM stage IV, indicating the therapy was primarily applied during the late phase of skeletal growth.

When comparing these demographics with findings from Tariq et al. (2024),¹² who investigated malocclusion prevalence among 500 adolescents aged 13–15 years in Karachi, a similar age range was observed. However, their sample showed a slightly higher male representation (56%) compared to our study. Notably, Tariq et al.¹² concluded that demographic factors such as gender and age did not significantly influence malocclusion prevalence, suggesting that while our sample had a higher proportion of older adolescents and females, this likely did not bias the clinical outcomes of Herbst therapy. Their study emphasized the influence of parental education and school enrollment on malocclusion patterns rather than intrinsic age or gender factors, which is not directly comparable to our focus on skeletal correction using functional appliances.

In the study by Hameed et al. (2023)¹³ conducted at Liaquat University Hospital, a broader adult age group (25–35 years) was assessed for malocclusion types and vertical discrepancies. Despite the older age range, their reported high prevalence of Class II malocclusion (12.4%) reinforces the need for early orthopedic intervention, such as that provided in our younger cohort. While the demographic profiles differ significantly, both studies highlight the clinical burden and frequency of Class II cases, validating the relevance of our sample choice during the adolescent growth phase. Similarly, Qamar and Chaudhry (2007)¹⁴ analyzed gender dimorphism among Class II malocclusion cases and found no statistically

significant skeletal differences between males and females, apart from a greater SN length in males. Our gender-balanced sample supports this observation, indicating that Herbst therapy outcomes are unlikely to be influenced by gender-based skeletal variations, aligning with Qamar’s conclusion that gender does not substantially modify Class II skeletal presentation.

Furthermore, Tabassum et al. (2021)¹⁵ emphasized the posterior displacement of the glenoid fossa in Class II malocclusion, which was more structurally defined than demographically influenced. Their findings validate the skeletal criteria used in our inclusion (retrognathic mandible with CVM stage III/IV) and underscore the necessity of assessing craniovertebral relationships—an aspect central to our cephalometric evaluation. Although Wadood et al (2023)¹⁶ and Khan et al (2023)¹⁷ focused on morphometric and angulation changes across malocclusion classes, their inclusion of Class II patterns among a younger Pakistani cohort further highlights the regional consistency in clinical presentation. These studies collectively reinforce the appropriateness of our study’s age range and gender distribution for investigating Class II correction using Herbst therapy in the context of local population trends.

Our findings align with those of Murali et al,¹⁸ who conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess the effects of functional appliances on cervical spine posture. Their results showed minor but consistent changes, including a 2.20° increase in middle cervical inclination and 1.60° increase in cervical curvature angle. These are comparable to the post-treatment increases in MP-CVT and MP-OPT angles observed in our study, reinforcing the notion that mandibular repositioning through fixed appliances can influence cervical spine alignment. Jaglan et al¹⁹ conducted a randomized controlled trial comparing Herbst and Advansync appliances, reporting anterior and inferior displacement of the hyoid bone and improvement in cervical posture.

Specifically, the mandibular plane-odontoid process angle decreased by 7.13° in the Herbst group, indicating enhanced cervical spine uprightiness, which mirrors our findings of increased post-treatment cervical angle values, such as SN-CVT and MP-CVT. Liu et al²⁰ examined cervical posture changes in patients treated with maxillary protraction appliances and found significant alterations primarily in the middle cervical region, with no notable changes in upper cervical posture. This selective regional response corroborates our data, where the greatest angular changes were observed in MP-CVT and MP-OPT, indicating a similar postural adjustment pattern even with different appliance mechanics.

The comparative effectiveness of fixed versus removable appliances was further discussed by Bahamid et al²¹ in their systematic review of Twin Block and Bionator devices. While both appliances were associated with mandibular advancement and TMJ repositioning, no significant differences were noted in skeletal effects. However, as their analysis focused on removable devices, our results suggest that fixed appliances like the Herbst may yield more pronounced and consistent changes in cervical posture due to continuous mandibular advancement. Sambale et al²² highlighted the influence of initial lip competence on treatment outcomes in Class II malocclusion. Patients with lip incompetence showed more significant mandibular advancement effects. Although lip posture was not evaluated in our cohort, the consistent direction and magnitude of postural change across patients suggest that the Herbst appliance effect on cervical spine posture may be robust, independent of soft tissue baseline variability.

The present study also supports the clinical implication emphasized by Murali et al¹⁸ that orthodontists should be aware of the extra-oral effects of functional therapy. Though the changes observed are moderate in degree, they can contribute to improved musculoskeletal harmony, potentially influencing airway dynamics, body posture, and long-term cervical health. A key strength of this study is the use of pre- and post-treatment cephalograms with consistent manual tracing for accurate angular measurement. The study was limited by a relatively small sample size (n=34), absence of a control group,

and lack of long-term follow-up to determine the permanence of postural changes. Additionally, individual variation in growth patterns and lip posture were not accounted for, which may influence outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Herbst appliance therapy in skeletal Class II patients results in significant and favorable changes in both hyoid bone positioning and cervical spine posture. These findings underscore the importance of considering cranio-cervical interactions during orthodontic planning. Future studies with larger sample sizes, control groups, and long-term follow-up are warranted to further validate these observations.

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